

Stability Analysis of Lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) Genotypes Across Multi-Year Normal and Late Sown Environments.

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Abstract

Genotype × environment interaction plays a critical role in determining yield stability of lentil under diverse agro-climatic conditions. The present study evaluated the phenotypic stability of twenty-nine lentil genotypes across six environments generated through normal and late sowing over three consecutive rabi seasons (2021–22, 2022–23 and 2023–24) at Baraut, Uttar Pradesh, India. Stability parameters were estimated using the Eberhart and Russell regression model. Pooled analysis of variance revealed significant effects of genotypes, environments, and genotype × environment interactions for seed yield and associated traits, indicating differential genotype responses across environments. Several genotypes exhibited high mean seed yield with regression coefficients close to unity and non-significant deviation from regression, indicating wide adaptability and stable performance. Genotypes with regression coefficients greater than unity were better adapted to favorable environments, while those with values below unity showed suitability for late sowing conditions. The study identified stable and high-yielding genotypes suitable for cultivation across diverse environments and for use as parents in lentil improvement programmes aimed at enhancing yield stability.

Keywords

Lentil, Genotype × Environment Interaction, Stability Analysis, Eberhart And Russell Model, Seed Yield.

Introduction

Lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) is an important cool-season pulse crop valued for its high protein content, adaptability to marginal soils, and role in sustainable agriculture through biological nitrogen fixation. Despite its importance, lentil productivity in many parts of India remains inconsistent due to fluctuating climatic conditions, delayed sowing, and variability in temperature during the reproductive phase. These factors often lead to strong genotype × environment interactions, which reduce the reliability of selection based solely on mean performance.

Yield stability has therefore become a key objective in lentil breeding programmes. A genotype with high yield potential but inconsistent performance across environments may not be suitable for wide cultivation. Conversely, genotypes showing stable performance across variable environments are preferred for varietal release, especially in regions where sowing time and climatic conditions vary considerably.

Among the available statistical approaches, the regression-based stability model proposed by Eberhart and Russell provides a reliable framework for evaluating adaptability and stability of genotypes across environments. This model considers mean performance, regression coefficient, and deviation from regression, allowing identification of genotypes with wide or specific adaptability.

Objective of study

The present investigation was undertaken to evaluate the stability of lentil genotypes under normal and late sowing conditions over multiple years, with the objective of identifying stable, high-yielding genotypes suitable for diverse agro-ecological conditions of northern India.

Review of Literature

Recent research has demonstrated the value of these models in lentil. Mishra *et al.* (2023) evaluated 20 genotypes across five environments and used both AMMI and GGE analyses to identify genotypes with either specific adaptation or broad stability. Their results highlighted

the usefulness of AMMI Stability Value (ASV) and Genotype Selection Index (GSI) in identifying desirable genotypes.

Khan *et al.* (2022) utilized similar methods and observed that genotypes with regression coefficients near one and minimal deviations were consistent performers. GGE biplots provided a graphical representation of genotype performance and helped identify optimal test environments.

Verma *et al.* (2021) assessed lentil lines under rainfed and irrigated settings and used these models to identify lines suited for specific environments. Likewise, Upadhyay *et al.* (2022) concluded that environmental variation had a stronger effect than genotypic differences, underscoring the need for multi-location testing.

Sharma *et al.* (2021) also emphasized that seed weight and pod number are the important traits for improving the lentil productivity across agro-climatic conditions.

In a longitudinal study, Sharma *et al.* (2022) evaluated genotype performance across three years and emphasized the importance of principal component analysis within the AMMI framework. Genotypes with low interaction principal component scores were identified as stable.

Sarkar *et al.*, 2022 recognized Wild lentil relatives such as *L. orientalis*, *L. ervoides*, and *L. nigricans* as valuable sources of genes conferring resistance to diseases and environmental stresses.

Recent reviews, such as that by Sarker *et al.* (2023), advocate for the integration of stability analysis with molecular tools like QTL mapping. Such integration is expected to enhance the precision and efficiency of genotype selection, especially under unpredictable climatic conditions.

Overall, studies underline the importance of combining genetic variability assessment with robust stability analysis. Identification of genotypes that not only perform well but also maintain consistency across environments is crucial for lentil improvement in the face of environmental variability. Multivariate models like AMMI and GGE, coupled with modern molecular tools, are shaping the next generation of lentil breeding strategies.

Methodology

Experimental Site and Plant Material

The experiment was conducted at the Research Farm of Janta Vedic College, Baraut, Baghpat, Uttar Pradesh, India, during three rabi seasons (2021–22, 2022–23 and 2023–24). Twenty-nine lentil genotypes obtained from ICAR-IIPR, Kanpur, were evaluated.

Experimental Design and Environments

The genotypes were grown in a randomized block design with three replications under six environments formed by two sowing dates each year:

- Normal sowing (E1, E3, E5)
- Late sowing (E2, E4, E6)

Each plot consisted of three rows of 3 m length with spacing of 30 cm between rows and 10 cm between plants. Recommended agronomic practices were followed uniformly.

Observations Recorded

Data were recorded on seed yield per plant and associated morphological traits from five randomly selected plants in each plot. Mean values were used for statistical analysis.

Analysis

Statistical Analysis

Pooled analysis of variance was carried out to test the significance of genotypes, environments, and genotype × environment interactions. Stability parameters were estimated using the Eberhart and Russell model, which includes:

- Mean performance across environments
- Regression coefficient (b_i)
- Deviation from regression (S^2d_i)

Genotypes with high mean yield, $b_i \approx 1$, and non-significant S^2d_i were considered stable and widely adapted.

Result and Discussion

Pooled Analysis of Variance

The pooled ANOVA revealed highly significant differences among genotypes and environments for seed yield. The genotype \times environment interaction was also significant, indicating that genotypes responded differently to environmental variations caused by sowing time and seasonal differences.

Analysis of Variance of Stability

Source of variation	DF	Days to Germination	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No of pri. branches / plant	No of sec. branches / plant	No of Pods / plant	No of seeds / pod	100- seed weight (g)	No of nodes upto first flower	No of Fruiting nodes/ plant	Protein content	Biological Yield (g/plant)	Harvest index (%)	Seed yield (g/ plant)
Varieties	28	2.01**	31.66**	8.99**	69.47**	0.129**	12.28**	261.70**	0.028**	0.427**	3.565**	16.05**	3.068**	37.83**	35.42**	1.118**
Environments	5	12.02**	356.54**	410.65**	178.72**	2.011**	15.01**	381.28**	0.179**	0.251**	0.129**	484.99**	0.115	53.59**	82.03**	0.999**
Variety X Environment	140	0.69	8.02**	5.71**	10.70**	0.090**	5.36**	79.28**	0.029**	0.111**	0.906**	8.93**	0.043	11.46**	14.39**	0.354**
Pooled Error	336	0.47	0.54	0.68	0.66	0.052	0.41	2.24	0.018	0.035	0.079	0.26	0.127	0.27	1.79	0.054
ENV+ (VAR.*ENV.)	145	1.08**	20.04**	19.67**	16.49**	0.156**	5.69**	89.69**	0.034**	0.115**	0.879**	25.35**	0.045	12.91**	16.72**	0.376**
Environ (Linear)	1	60.09**	1782.31**	2053.7**	893.65**	10.05**	75.02**	1906.13**	0.897**	1.252**	0.647**	2424.87**	0.639**	267.9**	410.11**	4.993**
Varxenviron (Linear)	28	1.96*	18.66**	9.93**	26.31**	0.103**	6.11**	104.61**	0.037**	0.105**	1.305**	26.16**	0.035	13.18**	20.30**	1.055**
Pooled Deviation	116	0.36	5.18	4.49	6.56	0.084	4.99	70.43	0.026	0.108	0.779	4.47	0.043	10.65	12.47	0.173
Total	173	1.23	21.92	17.94	25.07	0.152	6.76	117.53	0.033	0.166	1.314	23.85	0.535	16.94	19.75	0.496

Mean Performance of Genotypes

Mean seed yield across environments varied considerably among genotypes, reflecting substantial genetic variability. Normal sowing environments generally recorded higher mean yields compared to late sowing environments, although some genotypes maintained relatively stable yields under delayed sowing.

Regression Coefficient (b_i)

Regression coefficients ranged from values less than unity to greater than unity. Genotypes with b_i values close to unity exhibited average responsiveness and adaptability across environments. Genotypes with $b_i > 1$ showed better performance under favorable environments, whereas those with $b_i < 1$ were less sensitive to environmental changes and performed comparatively better under late sowing conditions.

Deviation from Regression (S^2d_i)

Deviation from regression varied among genotypes. Genotypes with low and non-significant S^2d_i values exhibited predictable performance and were considered stable. A few genotypes combined high mean yield with minimal deviation from regression, indicating both high productivity and stability.

Identification of Stable Genotypes

Based on combined consideration of mean yield, regression coefficient, and deviation from regression, several genotypes were identified as stable and widely adapted across environments. These genotypes demonstrated consistent performance under both normal and late sowing conditions over years.

Table 2a Mean, bi and sd2

SN	Genotypes	Days to Germination			Days to 50% Flowering			Days to maturity			Plant height (cm)			No of pri. branches/plant		
		Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi
1	IPL-526	7.72	0.71	0.00	80.00	1.62*	13.62	131.22	1.20	4.06	29.73	1.54*	1.60	3.22	1.72**	0.03
2	NARENDRA M-1	8.39	1.20	-0.05	80.33	-0.31	23.40	129.61	0.53	4.90	32.47	2.37**	12.56	3.16	1.42	0.04
3	IPL-534	7.72	1.46	0.03	82.78	1.02	1.20	131.56	1.40	2.08	32.64	-0.11	0.01	3.48	1.85**	0.15
4	BARI-6	8.56	1.38	0.28	82.28	-0.39	1.03	130.00	1.06	1.33	29.98	1.39	0.57	3.34	2.11**	0.07
5	PANT L-369	9.11	0.69	0.02	83.39	0.61	-0.06	129.94	0.98	3.59	33.48	0.27	5.29	3.53	1.77**	0.13
6	L-4147	8.72	1.29	-0.11	83.06	0.62	6.83	130.78	0.91	0.73	35.92	-0.40	31.47	3.53	0.56	0.15
7	PL-3	8.67	1.69*	0.20	77.94	1.34	0.67	129.39	1.34	3.16	27.90	0.20	0.94	3.27	0.94	0.00
8	HUL-57	10.00	3.04**	0.27	79.78	2.08	1.19	131.06	0.11	2.20	32.33	0.85	17.25	3.48	0.55	0.13
9	K-75	9.33	-0.40	-0.08	82.33	0.57	7.98	131.56	1.14	1.03	39.04	-0.35	17.71	3.47	1.31	0.13
10	IPL-321	7.83	0.91	-0.05	80.33	1.67	17.51	133.33	0.80	4.66	35.17	0.06	3.40	3.72	0.88	0.35
11	PANT L-406	8.06	0.25	0.67	81.00	0.99	5.68	131.11	0.75	2.60	31.61	0.52	7.55	3.24	1.29	0.00
12	DPL-15	8.28	1.12	0.05	78.22	1.33	-0.06	130.67	1.06	3.43	34.24	1.58*	7.37	3.28	1.06	0.03
13	IPL-315	8.56	1.85	0.32	78.67	1.11	0.75	130.61	0.49	1.89	33.07	2.23**	4.30	3.32	0.61	0.00
14	WBL-62	7.56	1.05	0.37	81.83	1.01	7.67	130.78	0.84	2.08	32.32	1.98**	5.08	3.26	1.19	0.02
15	IPL-81	7.78	0.93	0.93	77.61	1.43*	-0.01	132.22	1.11	1.16	34.76	1.62*	21.67	3.38	0.22	0.02
16	DPL-62	8.56	2.76**	0.37	79.22	1.13	0.13	133.39	0.41	3.08	31.67	2.38**	0.42	3.68	0.87	0.24
17	T-36	9.33	-0.04	0.40	81.89	0.35	3.82	131.89	1.09	0.61	35.51	1.71**	-0.04	3.22	0.60	0.00
18	IC-560128	9.22	0.95	0.58	80.83	1.40*	5.12	130.17	0.88	5.41	34.56	0.91	10.53	3.22	1.16	0.00
19	B-77	8.56	0.00	0.38	75.50	0.86	1.54	129.50	1.61	13.04	25.53	0.23	3.26	3.29	1.49*	-0.01
20	RANJAN	8.78	-0.65	-0.06	75.33	0.83	0.76	130.28	1.57*	18.97	29.66	-0.81	11.52	3.24	1.52*	0.02
21	L-4076	8.61	-0.63	0.16	80.22	0.73	7.77	131.28	1.29	8.87	35.30	2.03**	6.51	3.28	0.66	0.10
22	IPL-316	9.17	2.43**	0.26	79.72	0.25	3.96	131.28	1.04	0.99	37.09	2.30**	1.61	3.51	1.51*	0.09
23	BIM-5	8.22	-0.98	0.04	75.33	0.97	-0.10	128.67	1.85**	10.91	22.08	0.28	0.52	3.51	0.09	0.12
24	JL-1	9.00	0.88	0.33	78.94	1.38*	11.08	129.67	0.86	4.22	32.77	0.66	3.02	3.29	0.43	0.03
25	IPL-406	8.89	1.40	-0.14	79.11	1.45*	1.10	133.50	0.51	2.38	34.25	0.97	3.62	3.56	0.13	0.11
26	IPL-220	8.67	1.76*	0.12	80.72	1.50*	4.15	131.78	1.11	7.02	34.45	1.01	0.11	3.37	0.21	0.00
27	IPL-225	8.89	0.96	-0.04	81.83	1.11	2.65	130.89	0.95	-0.10	33.96	1.54*	0.00	3.31	1.00	0.02
28	IPL-329	8.17	1.74*	0.43	77.06	1.18	2.94	130.78	0.99	2.98	33.01	0.26	0.66	3.24	0.85	-0.01
29	HUL-56	9.17	1.24	0.14	77.22	1.16	12.73	132.78	1.11	6.46	33.28	1.77	5.31	3.31	1.03	-0.01
	Mean	8.603			79.74			131.02			32.68			3.370		
	Se mean	0.268			1.018			0.948			1.145			0.129		
	SE ± bi	0.416			0.290			0.252			0.461			0.492		

Table 2b Mean, bi and sd2

SN	Genotypes	No of sec. branches/plant			No of Pods/plant			No of seeds/pod			100-seed weight (g)			No of nodes upto first flower		
		Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi
1	IPL-526	15.69	-1.81**	2.56	124.30	2.70**	2.55	1.36	2.41*	0.02	3.52	1.42	0.04	11.98	14.34**	0.98
2	NARENDRA M-1	16.05	-0.69	2.19	130.41	1.48	41.43	1.35	0.19	0.03	2.56	0.27	0.01	11.68	1.55	0.54
3	IPL-534	17.03	0.91	1.20	138.41	-0.19	54.82	1.42	2.08	0.05	3.13	3.72**	0.18	12.00	0.47	1.37
4	BARI-6	14.96	2.34**	9.33	121.03	0.80	54.25	1.36	0.38	0.01	2.74	2.35	0.09	11.22	7.51*	0.45
5	PANT L-369	11.04	1.01	0.86	121.83	0.36	0.56	1.32	0.28	0.02	2.51	0.26	0.00	10.64	14.14**	1.15

6	L-4147	15.88	2.70**	2.61	131.00	0.49	181.75	1.49	0.36	0.03	2.45	-0.74	0.05	12.28	14.61**	0.59
7	PL-3	13.60	0.00	5.27	123.84	0.49	79.93	1.32	0.75	0.00	3.17	1.66	0.19	9.56	1.27	-0.02
8	HUL-57	13.16	0.72	2.27	125.00	1.63	46.06	1.36	-0.24	0.02	2.52	0.10	0.04	10.47	-1.50	0.01
9	K-75	12.70	1.08	0.43	124.47	0.03	19.83	1.29	1.76	0.01	3.09	1.73	0.12	10.23	-5.38	0.25
10	IPL-321	16.62	0.17	2.38	136.29	-0.66	18.15	1.46	2.43*	0.02	3.06	2.42	0.20	10.77	-1.46	1.35
11	PANT L-406	12.91	0.74	1.61	119.08	-1.89	120.99	1.28	0.61	0.01	2.77	-1.49	0.13	10.76	2.82	0.28
12	DPL-15	12.84	4.04**	2.34	116.16	0.98	1.97	1.31	0.86	0.02	2.75	0.17	0.26	10.41	0.49	-0.02
13	IPL-315	14.46	-0.87	1.64	121.47	2.29**	24.27	1.38	0.83	0.01	2.93	2.02	0.15	11.31	0.97	0.00
14	WBL-62	15.66	-1.47*	6.71	119.54	3.96**	91.23	1.33	1.99	0.04	2.72	2.69*	0.05	10.37	-7.74*	0.49
15	IPL-81	15.93	0.97	20.31	140.11	2.44**	75.85	1.48	1.96	0.04	2.97	1.41	0.10	11.29	-8.96**	1.72
16	DPL-62	15.94	2.15	6.54	124.49	2.56**	149.66	1.43	2.60**	0.01	2.85	2.49	0.12	10.96	-11.59**	1.11
17	T-36	14.54	2.68**	5.97	133.24	0.33	178.89	1.40	0.84	0.05	2.44	1.45	0.00	10.66	2.28	0.78
18	IC-560128	15.34	-0.59	4.06	119.81	2.17	23.84	1.38	2.56**	0.01	2.73	3.35**	0.16	9.85	-3.30	0.77
19	B-77	15.77	0.51	2.59	134.93	0.74	12.72	1.40	1.86	0.07	2.45	0.10	0.01	11.38	-0.79	0.00
20	RANJAN	15.50	1.13	8.31	128.53	0.12	9.62	1.49	-0.99	0.01	2.54	0.68	0.00	11.45	4.25	0.37
21	L-4076	14.01	1.71*	10.62	132.31	1.06	171.36	1.38	0.44	0.02	2.79	3.16**	0.12	11.15	-3.53	0.66
22	IPL-316	14.59	3.09**	4.09	123.23	0.15	91.67	1.31	1.87	0.01	2.49	-0.56	0.04	11.44	9.32**	0.71
23	BIM-5	14.42	2.42**	3.53	116.16	-0.10	182.30	1.50	-0.34	0.03	2.59	1.13	0.00	11.56	9.78**	1.49
24	JL-1	14.21	0.08	7.49	124.33	1.52	61.45	1.36	1.41	0.00	2.95	-2.56*	0.41	11.34	0.99	-0.01
25	IPL-406	15.14	0.99	10.13	127.57	2.39**	3.56	1.30	2.41**	0.00	2.46	-1.09	0.06	12.38	6.71	1.21
26	IPL-220	16.08	3.83**	2.63	131.02	-0.73	137.38	1.44	-0.63	0.02	2.88	2.35	0.10	12.15	7.75**	0.53
27	IPL-225	15.36	0.34	3.84	134.14	0.27	95.61	1.51	-1.20	0.00	2.60	1.41	0.00	11.59	-14.49**	1.24
28	IPL-329	14.29	-1.36	4.28	129.43	1.60	65.30	1.43	0.89	0.02	2.53	0.03	0.02	10.81	-11.09**	2.14
29	HUL-56	17.42	2.19**	5.11	133.82	2.00	23.83	1.46	0.64	0.01	2.76	-0.90	0.16	12.86	-0.53	1.69
	Mean	14.866			127.102			1.390			2.757			11.191		
	Se mean	0.999			3.753			0.072			0.147			0.395		
	SE ± bi	1.389			1.035			0.910			1.584			5.906		

Table 2c Mean, bi and sdi

SN	Genotypes	No of Fruiting nodes/plant			Protein content			Biological Yield (g/plant)			Harvest index (%)			Seed yield (g/plant)		
		Mean	Bi	Sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi	Mean	Bi	sdi
1	IPL-526	52.19	1.56**	0.02	21.99	2.22**	0.18	19.01	0.49	0.47	28.58	0.67	-0.57	5.42	-0.18	-0.01
2	NARENDR A M-1	52.00	1.41**	-0.07	21.67	0.10	0.23	22.58	0.50	12.55	25.68	-0.23	5.04	5.74	2.17	0.02
3	IPL-534	51.45	1.30*	0.77	21.49	-1.62*	-0.01	21.50	-0.16	2.98	27.76	0.29	8.25	5.94	1.97	0.02
4	BARI-6	50.64	0.93	5.95	22.21	2.11**	-0.03	19.80	0.22	7.75	27.72	0.73	2.83	5.45	-0.14	0.11
5	PANT L-369	49.79	0.23	1.21	23.22	2.00**	-0.02	16.11	0.41	8.21	30.27	-0.31	2.12	4.84	2.81**	0.00
6	L-4147	51.42	1.05	10.15	21.36	1.03	-0.04	22.86	-0.28	18.69	27.36	-0.43	23.78	6.16	4.95**	0.11
7	PL-3	49.96	1.75**	0.01	22.27	0.40	-0.02	17.00	0.54	7.14	30.37	1.48	1.47	5.11	-1.72	0.06
8	HUL-57	49.22	1.45**	9.60	22.34	1.43	-0.01	18.21	1.58	4.37	28.99	1.23	4.63	5.21	0.76	0.09
9	K-75	52.33	1.12	4.72	22.26	2.26**	-0.04	18.00	0.67	8.22	28.30	1.10	13.40	5.02	-1.42	0.06
10	IPL-321	52.76	1.45**	2.07	22.31	2.13	-0.02	23.57	-0.11	35.12	24.41	1.14	34.04	5.50	-0.69	0.05
11	PANT L-406	52.77	1.26*	1.45	23.35	3.01**	0.00	16.75	-0.19	13.42	31.68	1.40	34.97	5.17	1.47	0.18

12	DPL-15	51.03	0.97	6.46	21.47	-0.93	0.01	18.11	1.25	5.34	28.49	2.53**	6.08	5.07	1.61	0.22
13	IPL-315	52.71	1.26*	4.78	21.40	1.42*	0.03	20.50	2.11*	13.03	27.48	0.46	29.78	5.47	1.37	0.16
14	WBL-62	52.58	1.41**	2.38	22.34	0.43	-0.04	19.81	1.90	2.01	28.91	0.93	6.06	5.67	-0.71	0.44
15	IPL-81	54.28	1.65**	0.38	23.34	1.72*	-0.03	23.23	0.55	10.20	27.59	-0.84	2.87	6.43	-3.65**	0.88
16	DPL-62	53.07	1.58**	7.49	21.33	-0.48	-0.02	21.20	0.97	6.41	27.95	-0.10	8.95	5.88	-1.40	0.21
17	T-36	50.65	0.57	1.50	21.43	1.55*	-0.01	23.85	2.68**	0.41	24.68	2.91**	0.50	5.74	2.81**	0.03
18	IC-560128	50.72	1.64**	7.38	22.35	2.17**	-0.02	23.42	3.38**	2.02	23.93	3.19**	8.07	5.37	0.12	0.05
19	B-77	48.77	1.65**	12.29	23.33	-0.14	0.02	24.31	2.91**	0.26	21.87	2.44**	20.59	5.14	-2.40**	0.03
20	RANJAN	49.31	0.13	1.13	22.32	1.38	-0.01	22.54	0.27	5.84	24.07	0.86	5.33	5.38	-0.01	0.02
21	L-4076	50.14	1.03	8.67	21.50	-1.97**	-0.03	23.62	3.12**	18.28	24.85	1.95*	0.73	5.78	6.67**	0.27
22	IPL-316	49.25	0.67	5.60	21.41	1.23	-0.03	18.80	1.20	7.56	23.20	2.66**	11.78	4.30	-3.75**	0.31
23	BIM-5	47.47	0.01	4.12	23.34	1.92**	-0.02	17.28	-0.47	14.21	30.82	-0.86	0.33	5.31	5.06**	0.23
24	JL-1	49.83	0.32	6.50	23.30	0.84	-0.01	19.52	-0.97	12.10	26.00	0.73	27.52	4.95	1.15	0.20
25	IPL-406	51.56	1.28*	7.67	21.39	0.37	-0.01	21.83	2.48**	22.08	25.83	1.45	24.86	5.41	1.37	0.09
26	IPL-220	49.94	0.08	0.16	22.31	2.78**	-0.03	23.59	-0.61	24.09	24.29	-0.64	16.66	5.61	3.15**	0.27
27	IPL-225	48.22	-0.01	0.62	21.51	-0.32	0.01	23.55	0.69	33.16	25.52	-0.41	27.08	5.83	3.01**	0.07
28	IPL-329	49.08	0.65	5.87	22.38	-0.53	-0.03	20.43	1.83	7.57	25.85	1.89	15.24	5.16	1.78	0.23
29	HUL-56	51.19	0.60	8.25	21.47	1.29	0.00	21.78	2.03	2.66	26.83	2.78**	1.76	5.74	2.81**	0.09
	Mean	50.839			22.152			20.784			26.872			5.441		
	Se mean	0.946			0.093			1.459			1.579			0.186		
	SE ± bi	0.231			1.394			1.074			0.939			1.001		

Discussion

The significant genotype × environment interaction observed in the present study highlights the importance of multi-environment testing for reliable selection in lentil. Differences in sowing time and seasonal conditions influenced genotype performance, particularly for seed yield.

Genotypes exhibiting regression coefficients near unity and low deviation from regression were considered ideal, as they showed stable performance across environments. Such genotypes are valuable for varietal release and cultivation in regions with unpredictable sowing conditions. Genotypes with higher regression coefficients were more responsive to favorable environments and may be suitable for areas with assured timely sowing, while those with lower coefficients can be exploited for stress-prone or late sowing conditions.

The results confirm that stability analysis based on regression models is an effective tool for identifying adaptable and reliable genotypes in lentil breeding programmes.

Conclusion

The present investigation demonstrated the presence of significant genotype × environment interaction for seed yield in lentil. Stability analysis identified genotypes with wide adaptability and consistent performance across normal and late sowing conditions over multiple years. Stable lentil genotypes are HUL-57, IC-560128, RANJAN, JL-1, PANT L-406 (moderately stable), DPL-15 (moderately stable). These stable genotypes can be recommended for cultivation in diverse agro-climatic regions and utilized as promising parents in breeding programmes aimed at improving yield stability in lentil.

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